

APPLYING ENGLISH LANGUAGE TRANSFORMATION RESEARCH THEORY

Anna Tatarinceva

Professor, Dr.Paed. Baltic International Academy, Riga, Latvia
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Abstract: Learning a foreign language is a condition of human survival. To know foreign language, its history, borrowings, variants, dialects, accents means an extension of human identity, new possibilities to communicate with people from different nations.

Key words: accent, dialects, essence, variant, regional, social, phonemic, phonetic, language.

1 INTRODUCTION

The following features are widely regarded as “shibboleths”, especially when several ones occur together: a merger of the vowels in such pairs as “fair/fur” and “spare/spur” is recognized as an [e:] as in other parts of the north-west of England, syllable-final “-ng” is pronounced as in long-g for “long”, “sing-ging-g” for “singing”; the vowel in such words as “pin” and “sing” is pronounced [ɪ:], so they sound close to “peen” and “seengg”; the sound [r] may be either an alveolar continuant or an alveolar tap that is particularly distinct initially (“rabbit”, “run”), after stops and fricatives (“breathe”, “grass”, “three”) and between vowels (“carry”, “ferry”); a [t] between vowels is often replaced by [r], sometimes shown in print as [rr], as in “marra” for “matter”: “What is the marra with you then?”.

In a publicity drive for Liverpool clean streets campaign, litter was described as “norra lorra fun”; some speakers, especially the working-class Catholics of Irish background replace [t, d] with [ð], as in “dese tree” for “these tree”. “Month” may be pronounced [munth]; in syllable-initial and syllable-final position, a fricative can follow a stop, as in “k/x/ing” for “king”) where [x] represents the fricative in Scottish “loch”, “me”, “d/z/ad” for “my dad”, “back[x]” for “back”, and “bad[z]” for “bad”;

2 TECHNOLOGY FOR OBTAINING MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHOD

Scouse is often described as having a flat intonation, in effect a rise with a level tail where RP has a fall: in the statement “I don’t like it”, it goes up on “like” then runs level, whereas RP starts going down on “like” and keeps going down. There is also a kind of fall in “yes-no” questions where RP would have a rise, so that in the question “Are you from Birkenhead?”, Scouse falls on “Birk” where it rises in RP. Until recently it was possible to distinguish the speech of Irish Catholics from Protestant English through pronunciation of some words; a double advertisement on local buses in the 1960s read on one side of the bus “Treat us furly, travel early”, on the other “Treat us fairly, travel airly” (the

latter denoting Irish derived usage); unlike in other northern urban accents, the final vowel of words like “city”, “seedy” is [ɪ:]; [p, t, k] are heavily aspirated or even affricated.

Thus: can’t [k/x/ a: nt], straight [streits], “back/x/” for “back”. In final position, [p, t, k] there may be realized as fricatives [s, k]; [h] is usually absent, but sometimes is present - “him, her”, the suffix “-ing” is [ɪŋ]. The voice quality of speakers of Scouse was often described as “adenoidal”, and phoneticians speculated about the origins of such a feature.

According to Knowles (1986), the centre of gravity of the tongue is brought backwards and upwards, the pillars of the fauces are narrowed, the pharynx is tightened, and the larynx is displaced upwards in Scouse. The main auditory effect of this setting is the “adenoidal” quality of Scouse, which is produced even if the speaker’s nasal passages are unobstructed. The effect is primarily achieved by the sustained closure of the velum or soft palate.

The usage of the accent of Liverpool is limited to the city itself, to urban areas adjoining it, and to towns facing it across the River Mersey. While the accent is northern rather than southern in character, it differs in a number of ways from other northern urban varieties, including those of the rest of Lancashire, the county where Liverpool is located. Many famous songs by “Beatles” have their special charm typical for Scouse.

The East End of London grew with the spread of industries to the east of the City. It is also one of those areas of London where foreigners came to find a job, the East End is especially famous as the centre of clothing industry (or “rag-trad”) in London. The East End has many old properties, built already in Dickens’ time, many houses which the Londoners christened “slums”. The markets of the East End are famous throughout the world. The Petticoat Lane Market takes place every Sunday morning, it became one of the sights of London. Street-salesmen promise that the goods are of the highest quality and much cheaper than those you can buy in the West End! “Come on darlin’...amazin’ bargain...you ain’t seen nuffink like it!”

The majority of those lived in the East End are the hereditary inhabitants of the area. Their fathers, grandfathers and great-grandfathers were born there. They love the East End and are proud that they have the right to call themselves “Cockneys”.

The word “Cockney” is a fairly wide term, meaning “the true Londoner” or “an old resident of the East End”.

One of the strongest and most unusual accents is to be found in the East of London, at the home of “Cockneys”.

According to M. Mackenzie (1994), “Cockney” is a colloquial name applied to a Londoner born under the sound of Bow bells - the bells of the Church of St. Mary-Le-Bow, which stands nearly in the centre of the City of London.

The origin of this word was the subject of many guesses, but the historical examination of the various uses of “Cockney” by Sir James Murray (1991) shows that the earliest form of this word is “cokenay” or “cokeney”; i.e., “ey” or “egg”, and “coken”, the genitive plural of “cock”, “cocks’ eggs” being the name given to the small and malformed eggs sometimes laid by young hens.

Thus, Robert Whittington speaks of Cockneys in such a phrase - “it is used in great cities as London, York, Perugia (Perugia). It was not till the beginning of the 17th century that “Cockney” appears to be confined to the inhabitant of London.

The so-called “Cockney accent” was chiefly characterized by the substitution of a “v” for “w”, or vice versa in the first part of the 19th century. The chief consonantal variation existed now is perhaps the change of “th” to “f” or “v”, as in “fing” for “thing”, or “farver” for “father”. The vowel sound changed from “ou” to “ah”, as in “abaht” for “about”, were illustrated in the “Coster Songs” by Albert Chevalier (1987: 93).

The most marked change of the vowel sound is that of “ei” for “ai”, so that “daily” becomes “dily”. The omission of “h” is not peculiar to Cockney. The Cockney accent is not a particularly pleasant or melodious one, and the Cockney’s distortion of the English language is such that the foreigner often finds it impossible to understand the speaker until his ear acclimatizes to the peculiar tones.

According to Meredith (1991), this accent, known as the “Cockney slang”, was first developed by the representatives of the Underworld in the 1860s when thieves and crooks were able to pass information among themselves and confuse the police and other law-abiding citizens at the same time.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND THEIR DISCUSSION

“Cockney” is, of course, the southern accent. The Cockney language is really more than an accent, since it includes many words and expressions that cannot be heard in any other part of the country. The principal characteristics of the Cockney accent consist in a general slurring of consonants (the aspirate aitch is often ignored) and a distortion of vowel sounds. Cockney is very different from the idea of a typical speech of an Englishman.

According to E. Partridge (1992), “Cockney” exists on two levels:

- **as spoken by the educated lower middle classes, it is a social dialect marked by some deviations in pronunciation but few in vocabulary and syntax;**
- as spoken by uneducated, “Cockney” differs from Standard English not only in pronunciation but also in vocabulary, morphology and syntax.

«The Encyclopaedia Britannica» treats “Cockney” as an accent, not acknowledging it the status of the dialect. A linguist Rastorguyeva (1983:159) believes that “Cockney” is the dialect of London. The history of this dialect reveals the sources of the literary language in the late Middle English. The Early Middle English records made in London in 1258 show that the dialect of London was fundamentally East Saxon; in terms of the ME division, belonged to the South-Western dialect group.

The most likely explanation of the change of the dialect type and of the mixed character of London English lies in the history of London population. The inhabitants of London came from the south-western areas of England in the 12th - 13th centuries. London had over 35000 inhabitants by the 1377. Most of the new arrivals came from the East Midlands: Norfolk, Suffolk, and other populous and wealthy counties of Medieval England. As a result the speech of Londoners was much closer to the East Midland dialect.

As recorded by Ch. Dickens over a century ago, “Cockney” was phonetically characterized by the interchange of the labial and labio-dental consonants [w] and [v]: “wery” for “very”, and “vell” for “well”. The voiceless and voiced dental spirants are still replaced - though not very consistently - by [f] and [v] respectively: “fing” for the word “thing”, and “farver” for the word “father”. Then there is the interchange of the aspirated and non-aspirated initial vowels: “hart” for “art”, and “eart” for heart in Cockney. The most marked feature in the vowel sound

is the substitution of the diphthong [ai] for standard [ei] in such words as: “day”, “face”, “rain”, “way” pronounced: [dai], [fais], [rain], [wai]. Cockneys don't pronounce their [h], e.g. “house” is pronounced [ouse], “here” is pronounced [ere] and, “plate” - [late], “plite” – [lite] .

There are some specifically Cockney words and set expressions such as [up the pole]- “drunk” , [you' ll get yourself] “disliked” (a remonstrance to a person behaving very badly).

Cockney is lively and witty, its vocabulary is imaginative and colourful. Its specific feature not occurring anywhere else is so-called “rhyming slang “. The rhyming slang was used a lot by the performers in the old music halls in the early 1900s. According to Brewer (1986); “rhyming slang” – slang, much used by the Cockneys, in which the word intended is replaced by one that rhymes with it, as:

[apples and pears] for “stairs”,
[butcher's hook] for “look”,
[plates of meat] for “feet “,
[Rory O' More] for “door”,
[dicky dirt] for “shirt”,
[dicky bird] for “ word”,
[left and right] for “fight “,
[mince pies] for “eyes”,
[Micky Mouse] for “house”,
[this and that] for “flat”,
[loaf of bread] for “head”,
[Uncle Ned] for “bed”,
[bees and honey] for “money”,
[custard and jelly] for “telly” (television)...

When the rhyme is a compound word the rhyming part is often dropped, leaving the uninitiated somewhat puzzled.

Thus, [Chivy (Chevy) Chase] rhymes with “face” , by dropping [chase], [Chivy] remains. For example;

 [“Use your loaf!”] means “Use your head...don't be silly!”

And [“ Let me have a butcher's”] means “ Let me have a look.”

Similarly, [daisies] are “boots”, from [daisy roots] , the [roots] were being dropped. Raspberry is a [heart (or vulgarly, [fart]), contracted from a [raspberry tart]. Numerous colloquial expressions derive from it, as : [that's a fiddle] , from [Yiddisher fiddle] (the musical instrument) which rhymed with [diddle].

This type of slang in the Cockney dialect arose due to the necessity to communicate without any witnesses (especially, police) in overcrowded districts of poor people. “Boots”, for instance, are called [daisy roots], a “hat” is [tit for tat], a “head” is sarcastically called [loaf of bread], and a “wife” - [trouble and strife] ...

It sets expression of its own. Here is an example of a rather crude phrase for somebody being dead: [« She may have pulled me through me operation, «] said Mrs Fisher, [« but 'streuth I'm not sure I wouldn't be better off pushing up the daisies, after all.»] (C.Dickens). The vocabulary of the dialect is remarkable for its conservatism - many words that became obsolete in Standard English are still kept in its dialects, e.g. and “envy” < OE andian;
[barge pig]< OE berg ;
[bysen blind] < OE bisene and others, where OE is Old English. If one keeps one's ears open on buses, in railway stations, in street markets and similar places, it will soon become evident that the spirit of Cockney humour is still alive, although the old Cockney pronunciation is less common than hitherto.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Dialects, accents and variants of English are the essential components of the history of the language, culture and history of Great Britain. Helping people to achieve intercultural sensitivity, establishing a willingness to understand, creating an open-minded attitude towards their own and the target cultures through implementing the language and its variants, in all these ways foreign language teaching can contribute to the students' personal growth, development and life-long intercultural learning and communication.

We should study and save all variants of the English language of contemporary Great Britain and successfully implement them nowadays

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